

Supplement of

Influence of secondary ice formation on tropical deep convective clouds simulated by the Unified Model

Mengyu Sun et al.

Correspondence to: Mengyu Sun (mengyu.sun@manchester.ac.uk)

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Figure S1. Time–height plots of ice water content (IWC; g m^{-3}) for simulations: (a) all-SIP, (b) no-SIP, and the difference between allSIP and noSIP simulations (i.e., allSIP minus noSIP). Panels (a–c) are averaged over regions where $\text{IWC} > 0.01 \text{ g m}^{-3}$. The 0, -20, -40, and -60 °C isotherms are shown by the dashed lines.

Figure S2. Same as Figure S1, but for rain water content (RWC; g m^{-3}). RWC values are averaged over the area where either the ice water path or rain water path exceeds 1 g m^{-2} .